

Use of Social Media Apps for Cyberstalking during Pandemic COVID-19 Lockdown: A cross-sectional Survey at University Students of Lahore

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Abstract

Cyberstalking is wrongdoing where the aggressor bugs a casualty utilizing elec-tronic correspondence, for example, email or texting (IM), or messages presented on a Web website or a conversation gathering. A cyberstalker depends upon the namelessness managed by the Internet to permit them to follow their casualty without being identified. The study's objectives were to discover university stu-dents' knowledge about cyberstalking and investigate which online tool was pri-marily used for cyberstalking during pandemic COVID-19 lockdown. A cross-sectional study was collected by the public and private universities of La-hore. All the participants' academic year was 2017 to 2020. This study included the University of Management and Technology, University of Lahore, Punjab University, University of South Asia, and University of Central Punjab students. A quantitative research design was used for this research. This study was descrip-tive. The population of the study were all public and private universities in Lahore. The sample were consisted of 272 participants who enrolled in university first, second, 3rd and 4th semesters; 146 male and 126 female BS, Masters and M.Phil participants were included. All participants enrolled in universities. A purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data. The researcher personally devel-oped the instrument for this study. 3 Likert type scales (yes, no, somehow) were used in this research. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Each factor in-cludes some statements according to the factor. The validity of the instrument was making sure of the experts of the field. The reliability of the instrument was calculated at 0.896 Cronbach alphas. Study results were analyzed by using the software Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21. Frequency distribution Mean, standard deviation, T-test and ANOVA were calculated. Results of the study show that university students have no complete knowledge about social media rules and cyberstalking. Never any university held a seminar or discussed these issues with students. The majority of the students think that only share photos without permission, thread, sexual harassment is called cyberstalking. According to the university, students in university stalkers mostly stalk rich girls during the pandemic lockdown. Cyberstalkers used social media apps to stalks other persons during the pandemic lockdown. WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook apps are mainly used for stalking during the lockdown. Twitter, messages and emails are not common social media apps for stalking at the university level. Mostly stalkers use online data to harass another person. Online pictures, videos help stalkers to do these types of activities. It is recommended that there is a need for a more profound and clear study on the problems of social media apps used for cyberstalking everyone without any security. Many sampling in different cities gives more quick results and help lawmakers modify the laws according to the situation.

Introduction

Cyberstalking is, for the most critical part, characterized as "utilizing the Internet, email, and other electronic correspondence gadgets to stalk someone else (Parsons-Pollard et al. (2009). Cyberstalking might be conceptualized as an expansion of stalking that uses PCs and other electronic gadgets or as an isolated activity with a portion of the components of stalking yet uses an alternate method of conveyance (Parsons-Pollard and Moriarty (2008). No solid pervasiveness figures for cyberstalking exist. One massive investigation of 4446 haphazardly chosen female students noticed that 13.1% of the example had been stalked. Of these, 24.7% had

gotten messages from the stalker, and messaging was the 6th generally normal stalking conduct detailed for study (Fisher et al. (2000).

A senior authority noticed that online networking buzz got from 0.4 million in January and 1.6 million in February to a stunning 20.3 million by March 24. The number purportedly spiked at the same time as crown infection cases hopped from only one in January to more than 500 in March. As the COVID-19 pandemic got us secured at home, web-based life became one of the key ways to keep in contact with others. Tragically, it's not just your closest and dearest who are following your isolated life. A wide range of miscreants could be keeping an eye on defenceless individuals, hanging tight for an opportunity to assault. The British police said the lockdown had brought a 26% expansion in badgering via web-based networking media and video meeting applications. Be that as it may, it's not just cyberstalking you ought to be stressed over. The substance itself, i.e., pictures and recordings you post on the web, can uncover much more to outsiders than you would at the first mean (Balram (2020).

It is excellent that Pakistan is keeping pace with the digital world. In the ongoing past (the year 2013), Pakistan crossed 10 million Facebook clients (half of them between 18-24). Of these clients, 2.8 million sign in to Facebook utilizing a cell phone. Cyberstalking could be compared to verbal surge, mudslinging, and individual data abuse to annoy or malign certifiable people purposely. The ongoing and conspicuous models in Pakistan are cricketer Saeed Ajmal and the Army Chief, Gen. Raheel Sharif. The two have counterfeit fan pages and Facebook accounts, which are being trailed by a decent number of Internet clients (Rizvi (2014).

In addition, Pakistan turned into the seventh most famous nation on the world's most important long-range interpersonal communication site. Likewise, many phoney records are adding to the pool of Facebook clients, and digital stalkers are among them.

The Internet has gotten a mechanism for individuals to convey locally or all-inclusive throughout the business, instruction, and public activities. The Internet has made it simple for individuals to contend, meet a friend, or speak with individuals on the opposite side of the world with the snap of a mouse. In 2009, as indicated by the Internet World Stats Report, 237,168,545 individuals utilized the Internet in the United States; thus, there is a worry for Internet security. The expanded Internet utilisation has affected the quantity of web-based cyberstalking cases (Paulet et al., 2009).

Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic was confirmed inside Pakistan in February. On March 13, 2020, in the evening, all news channels in Pakistan announced that all educational institutes of Pakistan would be closed by tomorrow till 15 July 2020 due to COVID-19. The choice was taken in a gathering of the National Security Committee, directed by the Prime Minister of Pakistan. The Interior Ministry requested the "total" enclose of the nation's border with neighbouring Iran and Afghanistan from March 16 following the National Security Committee choice for an underlying time of about fourteen days "to the most significant advantage of the three kindly nations. On 21 May 2020, there are 48,091 people of the COVID-19 have been confirmed in Pakistan. Out of which 14155 people have been recovered, and 1017 have died. In Punjab, 17,382 cases identify a primarily high number compared to another city of Pakistan (WHO (2020).

Shahid (2014) discussed that revealed innovation abuse ranges from sites being hacked to falsification and budgetary extortion. In any case, of the above 30 enlisted offences submitted through the web, it is cyberstalking that tops the rundown. More than 80% of the considerable number of objections enrolled with the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) opposite the web relating to this. The vast majority of the exploited people are young ladies confronting shakedown, provocation and blackmail. Furthermore, much of the time, those hurt are the exploited people as well as their families. Occurrences of coercion and badgering are not restricted to long-range informal communication locales, for the most part, Facebook and Twitter once in a while. The FIA has likewise run over situations were transformed, or veritable pictures, the contact subtleties of people or the telephone quantities of relatives were transferred on OLX.com, a well-known web-based showcasing site.

Despite mainstream thinking, Covid-19 isn't the principal 'advanced info emic'. In the ongoing past, episodes of Zika in Brazil, Ebola in Africa, Influenza in Europe and Nipah in India had comparable bidirectional associations with media. Be that as it may, the level of 'media alarm', the measure of media utilization and the subsequent change in open response have been a lot higher during Covid-19. On an alternate note, youngsters and teenagers presented to progressively online time will, in general, create innovation and gaming fixation. Remember that specific undesirable propensity will long outlive the pandemic to cause proceeded with issues throughout everyday life. Further, web-based energy-related fault and othering can likewise prompt disgrace, minimization, communalism and viciousness, particularly at such seasons of emergency. Individuals from the Northeast, specific strict networks and lower financial classes like the vagrants and destitute have just been casualties of such belittling (BANERJEE (2020).

Alexy et al. (2005) conducted a study on cyberstalking at a college level. This study developed an assemblage of research exploring the wonder of cyberstalking. Members comprised 100 enrolled students from a state college and 656 enrolled students from a vast private college. Information was accumulated from selected students about reactions to a cyber-stalking situation and their utilization and encounters with the Internet. Moreover, an examination and correlation of understudies who announced having been stalked to the

individuals who had been cyber stalked were finished. A startling discovery was that male students were more likely than female students to have been cyberstalked, and Caucasian guys had the most meaningful connection. The end demonstrates that the stalking culprit was the best bet to be a previous close accomplice for those cyberstalked. For this, health professionals are recommended for cyberstalkers.

Abbasi (2017) discussed that 40% of ladies in Pakistan face different types of badgering on the web, with most objections made identified with a provocation on Facebook, an ongoing report by the Digital Rights Foundation (DRF) has uncovered. A stunning 72% of ladies in the nation have no mindfulness about the digital wrongdoing laws managing on the web provocation, including web-based life destinations like Facebook, Twitter, and so on, expressed Pakistan's "first quantitative research study on online brutality".

Maqbool (2017) reported that cyberstalkers generally defraud females, albeit a couple of men have griped of being hassled as well. It is a wrongdoing were the aggressor bugs by utilizing electronic correspondence, such as email, web-based life, texting like Viber, WhatsApp, etc. The obscurity is a preferred position for a Cyberstalker. Under the new Cyberlaw went in Pakistan, there is a three-year detainment and fine of one million rupees in the event that you report cyberstalking.

In Pakistan, cybercrime can be categorized in different terms. Hacking, Identity theft, Cyber Bullying, Cyberstalking, Financial fraud, Digital Piracy etc., all are included in cybercrimes. Utilizing the Internet to compromise or make unwelcome advances towards another person Cyberstalking (additionally called cyber badgering) is the point at which somebody operates the Internet to undermine or make unwanted advances towards another person. This kind of provocation can cause physical, enthusiastic, and mental harm to the person in question. Kids are especially defenceless due to their confiding in nature ("Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) ministry of interior, the government of Pakistan").

Haider (2017) discussed that with irresponsible utilization of innovation, the instances of cyberstalking in Pakistan are ascending as in most recent one year 67% ladies out of complete 1551 protests revealed some sort of online provocation. Digital Rights Foundation (DRF) has discharged its "Digital Harassment Helpline: One-Year Report". During its first year, the Helpline has gotten 1,551 grievances as calls, messages, and Facebook messages from December 1, 2016, till November 30, 2017. 67% of the rings at the Helpline were by ladies, while 33% of the guests were men. Facebook remains the most generally revealed stage, with 45% of guests encountering badgering there. While 19% of the persons who call would not like to unveil their area, we had the option to distinguish that the vast majority of our guests on the Helpline were from Punjab (half). The Helpline additionally got calls from Sindh (18%), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (5%), Balochistan (2%), Azad Kashmir and FATA (1%) and the Federal Capital, Islamabad (5%).

Shahid et al. (2018) said that cyberstalking and cyber badgering research has distinguished the accompanying PC or media transmission-based provocation mediums including: Monitoring email correspondence, sending email that undermines, affronts or bothers, disturbing email interchanges by flooding an injured individual's email box with undesirable mail or by sending an infection program, utilizing the unfortunate casualty's email character to send bogus messages to other people or to buy merchandise and enterprises, utilizing the Internet to look for and accumulate a victim's close to home data for use in provocation, remailers (Email sent through an outsider where the headings are evacuated, making it basically challenging to follow its causes), spamming, unending Instant Messaging (IM) or messaging, posting in fitting messages or stalking practices in chat rooms, posting improper messages or stalking procedures on release sheets, blog destinations, as well as on informal communication webpage individual pages, site tributes and individual information control.

Dominelli (2017) reported that in Pakistan Telecom meeting from 191 million Pakistan Population, 18% of Pakistani use web which implies 34.4 million. Online networking or facebook clients are 14%. Versatile clients are 66% or 126.3 million. Versatile web-based life clients are 12% or 22 million. The report further shows that ladies facebook clients are 22%, which implies 27 million.

Agha and Magsi (2017) conducted a study on cyber harassment and the need for space on 100 female understudies of two genuine part colleges in Sindh, Pakistan. The paper talks about the occurrences of badgering and show that the female understudies were compromised, what's more, constantly extorted on the college grounds, for the most part by aggressors known to them. Yet, the understudies were hesitant to report badgering to their guardians or to carry it to the notification of their separate college specialists in light of the absence of trust and dread of harming the family's social standing. Based on discoveries from this investigation, proposals are made to coordinate an educational program on cyberbullying and build up a non-compromising correspondence framework between college understudies and the organization to report all ambushes. An expanded degree of trust and classification about the unfortunate casualty will, in the long run, help follow the instances of digital badgering. It will prompt the discipline of the violators.

Despite the deficiency of information around online provocation in Pakistan, the official detailing gives some knowledge along the degree of the issue. The Federal Investigation Authority (FIA) has expressed that in 2015 just 5% of instances of badgering were detailed and pursued by the lawful activity of any kind. The authority has likewise independently called attention to that during 2015, around 3,000 wrongdoings were

accounted for, and 45% of these comprised of ladies being focused via web-based networking media (Sattar et al. (2018). The purpose of the present study was to find out the knowledge of university-level students about cyberstalking. Is students use the right of cyberstalking in their life or not. This study also helps determine which social media medium is primarily used for cyberstalking during pandemic COVID-19 lockdown. The cyberstalking is most common crime use nowadays in Pakistan, especially during the pandemic lockdown. Here researchers selected private and public universities students to find about the cyberstalking ratio during the pandemic lockdown. University students have no enough knowledge about the law of cyberstalking, and mostly students never use this right if someone is stalking them. Female university students mostly lurk through social media apps during a pandemic. In Pakistan, no seminar was held to aware society and students about cyberstalking. Many girls and even boys committed suicide or go into depression because of cyberstalking. Even in universities, teachers never think it is essential to discuss cyberstalking. However, to solve this problem, this study finds out how to promote cyberstalking during the lockdown and overcome this problem in society. The study's objectives were to discover university students' knowledge about cyberstalking and investigate which online tool was mainly used for cyberstalking during pandemic COVID-19 lockdown. The inclusion criteria of this study were participants who enrolled in public and private universities in Lahore. Participants did B.S, M.A and M.PIL in semesters 1 to 4. All participants age was between 20 to 29 years old. Limitations of the study were only Lahore city was selected for this study. All the participants choose from Lahore universities. Student's degrees and age are included in the regulation of the study. Male and female fresh university students were also selected for this study.

Research Methodology

A cross-sectional study was collected by the public and private universities of Lahore, which include both male and female participants during data collection. This study included a total of 272 male and female students studying in the first, second, third and fourth semesters enrolled in university. All the participants' academic year was 2017 to 2020. This study included the University of Management and Technology, University of Lahore, Punjab University, University of South Asia and University of Central Punjab students.

Research Design

A quantitative research design was used for this research, and its information has been taken according to this topic. Keeping the limits of qualitative research in mind, the quantitative research design was adopted for this study also ensures the accuracy and credibiarch. The nature of the study was descriptive. This research describes the knowledge and understanding of university-level students about cyberstalking and knows which online tool was mainly used for cyberstalking during the pandemic lockdown in Lahore.

The population of the study was all public and private universities in Lahore. The sample size of this study consisted of 272 participants who enrolled at the university level. In this study, 146 male and 126 female BS, Masters and M.Phil participants were included. All participants enrolled in universities. A purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data.

The researcher personally developed the instrument for this study. Three Likert type scales (yes, no, somehow) were used in this research. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part was based on demographic information in which include (gender, age, qualification, university, semester, employ, social media user, social media medium used primarily and time of social media medium use). The second part is divided into five factors (Knowledge about cyberstalking, Online communication ways use for cyberstalking, **experience related to cyberstalking or harassment, Social media role in cyberstalking during lockdown and Relations who stalk according to them**). Each factor includes some statements according to the factor. The validity of the instrument was made sure by the experts of the field. The reliability of the instrument was calculated 0.896 Cronbach alphas.

Study results were analyzed by using SPSS-21. Frequency distribution Mean, standard deviation, T-test and Anova were calculated. Value of $P < 0.005$ is considered significant.

Results of the Study

Table 1

Statement Wise Mean and Standard Deviation

Sr. no	Statements	Mean	SD
1	In your opinion cyberstalking is Someone collect your data and harass you personally	1.36	0.639
2	Share photos without permission are called cyberstalking	1.35	0.636
3	Cyberstalking only effect and victim the rich girls during a pandemic	1.96	0.581
4	During study ever teachers discuss this and rights	2.07	0.779
5	Facebook is a famous form of cyber use to stalk during lockdown	1.66	0.812
6	Online database stalkers are mainly used for stalking	1.90	0.769
7	Messages are mostly used to harass	1.53	0.753
8	Have you ever been a victim of cyberstalking	1.81	0.641
9	Do you ever report any case related to this	1.91	0.631

10	The use of social media is a reason to increase the rate of cyberstalking during a pandemic	1.34	0.646
11	Is social media play any positive role to prevent cyberstalking during a pandemic	1.79	0.706
12	Media highlight these types of crimes during lockdown increase	1.64	0.769
13	Does government play any positive role for this purpose?	2.22	3.836
14	Is social media some apps that help stalkers to do these activities more during a pandemic	1.57	0.839
15	Work colleges person mostly stalking or include in these activities Ex-partner harass mostly?	1.96	0.659
16	Do friends harass because of a personal clash?	1.72	0.784
17		1.61	0.812

N=272

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation values of each statement of the questionnaire.

Table 2

Independent sample t-test on Gender

Factors	Male (146)		Female (126)		df	T	P
	M	SD	M	SD			
Knowledge about cyberstalking	11.60	2.183	13.75	2.439	270	7.646	.309
Online communication ways use for cyberstalking	12.44	2.369	12.54	2.679	270	-.331	.104
Experience related cyberstalking or harassment	14.61	2.760	14.90	2.671	270	-.869	.638
Social media role in cyberstalking during a pandemic	11.15	2.552	12.19	7.299	270	1.611	.002
Relations who stalk according to them	5.38	1.420	5.19	1.506	270	1.087	.977

Table 2 shows the result of an Independent sample t-test applied to find out the differences between male and female students' perceptions regarding knowledge and perception about cyberstalking. Results demonstrate a significant difference between males and females in one factor of social media role in cyberstalking $t(270) = 1.611, p = .002$. According to the other factors results there was no significant difference between male and female students about cyberstalking $t(270) = 7.646, p = .309$; $t(270) = -.331, p = .104$; $t(270) = -.869, p = .638$ and $t(270) = 1.087, p = .977$ commonly which were no less than alpha 0.05.

Table 3

One way ANOVA comparison of which social media apps mostly use

Factors	sum of square	F (2, 269)	P
Knowledge about cyberstalking	1745.515	15.461	.000
Online communication ways use for cyberstalking	1711.941	5.045	.007
Experience related cyberstalking or harassment	2001.985	.719	.448
Social media role in cyberstalking During pandemic	7677.235	23.133	.000
Relations who stalk according to them	578.471	.104	.901

Table 3 shows the results of one way ANOVA, which was applied to find out the university students knowledge about cyberstalking, online communication ways used for cyberstalking, students experience related to cyberstalking, and the role of social media in cyberstalking based on social media app primarily used for this purpose. Results indicate a significant difference in social media apps usage for cyberstalking (Knowledge about cyberstalking) $F=15.461, P=.000$ (**Social media role in cyberstalking**) $F= 23.133, p = .000$, which p-value was less than to significant value 0.005. An important difference exists in knowledge about cyberstalking and **Social**

media role in cyberstalking. (Online communication ways use for cyberstalking) $F=5.045$ $P= .007$; (Students experience related cyberstalking) $F=.719$, $P=.448$; (**Relations who stalk according to them**) $F-.104$, $p=.901$ which was not less than alpha 0.05. Results also show that there was no significant difference exists in the three factors of cyberstalking.

Table 4

Frequency analysis which time students use social media app mostly

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	St. Deviation
At Evening	24	8.8		
At University	132	48.8	3.40	.646
At Night	116	42.6		

Table 4 shows frequency analysis of time social media app mostly used by university students. Results show that at evening time (8.8 %), participants mostly used Apps. At university time (48.8 %), participants used social media apps and at night time (42.6 %), participants mostly used social media different apps. The majority of the participants frequently use social media app in university. Overall Mean= 3.40, SD= .646 was calculated.

Table 5

Frequency analysis which social media app mostly use for cyberstalking during a pandemic

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	St. Deviation
WhatsApp	91	33.5		
Instagram	3	1.1	6.32	.943
Snapchat, WhatsApp, Instagram (3 apps at a time)	178	65.4		

Table 5 shows frequency analysis of which social media apps are primarily used for cyberstalking during a pandemic for university students. These apps promote cyberstalking slowly. Results show that 33.5% of participants mostly used WhatsApp. 1.1 % of participants used Instagram frequently. 65.4% of participants primarily used social media, different apps at a time. Participants used (WhatsApp, Instagram and Snapchat) frequently at one time. The Mean value of social media apps was = 6.32, SD= .943.

Table 6

All factors results show in a graph

factors results in a Graph

Table 6 shows the responses rate of participants in all statements with the help of the graphs bar. The majority of the participants answered the yes scale. 80% of participant's answers fall in yes. 15% of participant's responses lose in somehow scale. Only 5% of participant's responses fall in the "No" Likert type scale.

Discussion:

Nowadays, cyberstalking is an online crime. Cyberstalkers stalk other persons through social media apps. Stalking itself is certifiably not another wrongdoing, yet digital stalking is another approach to carry out the mischief of stalking while at the same time utilizing the Internet or different types of specialized electronic gadgets. Stalkers, both on the web and disconnected, are propelled by the craving to apply power over their exploited people and participate in comparable sorts of conduct to achieve this end (Ogilvie (2000). University students have no complete knowledge about social media rules and cyberstalking. Never any university held a seminar or discussed these issues with students. The majority of the students thinks that only share photos without permission, thread, sexual harassment is called cyberstalking. According to the university, students in university stalkers mostly stalk rich girls. Cyberstalkers used social media apps to stalks other persons during the pandemic lockdown. WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook apps are mainly used for stalking. Twitter, messages and emails are not common social media apps for stalking at the university level. Most stalkers use online data for harassment. Online pictures, videos help stalkers to do these types of activities. Tiktok app nowadays is very famous for using for this crime. The majority of people make their videos and upload them in this app. After this, everyone downloads this video and share it in their circle. The government of Pakistan makes a law against this crime. The act's name is Controversial cybercrime law called the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act, 2016, but no one is aware of this criminal act. Some of the people file cases against cyberstalking. Majority of the girl's face this type of issues and girls never shows to their family member or in a society that someone stalks her or harasses. Girls face and sometimes leave the study before completing the study. Cyberstalking is effect the study and mind of the students. Students feel stress and disturbance to get unknown threatening messages. University teachers also do these type of activities & crime with students.

Exciting news shows through this result that not a hostel university student mostly stalks, but the students living own city mostly stalks and face this problem. Hostel students can stand against these issues, but students living in their town never take a step or stand against this issue. University students use the Internet 24 hours. They use all social media apps continuously during a pandemic but use social media apps at university. At night they spend their time in WhatsApp, Snapchat and Instagram to chat with friends. Most students get harassment messages and calls at night because all the students are awake and online on social media during the lockdown. People read stalkers messages and reply for don't text me; this is a way stalkers know other people respond. In Pakistan, the government makes a law, and the punishment rule is to pay 5 million rupees and 14 years in jail. But not a proper check and balance exist in this department. No one file the case, and the team feel relaxed and never try to do something different for stalkers.

Media highlight all types of crimes, but in the end, all fail. Recently many cases raise through media and many people in cities and underdeveloped areas try to do something for their country. The press should propose new ways to prevent cyberstalking in society during these pandemics or lockdown situations and how stalkers are arrested. Best friends, ex-partners, and old work colleagues used your data and information for stalking. The majority of the people stalks through their friends. Friends have complete personal information, pictures, and videos of their friends that help in stalking. Government should make a separate committee and higher best members in this committee who take a step to prevent this crime.

Conclusion:

According to the study results, it is concluded that cyberstalking is the most common way to choose friends, colleagues, and ex-partners to stalks other persons during a pandemic. Online social media apps are primarily used for stalking during the pandemic lockdown. University students are mostly part and victims of this crime. WhatsApp, Snapchat, Instagram, and Facebooks apps mostly used students 24 hours. At university, students frequently used these apps also in the class. Students make a group and share all photos etc., in this group. On Facebook, people share their stories and streaks, and all these accounts are published. It is concluded that university students don't allow students to use cell phones in class. Student always uses privacy in their accounts. University students must take steps against this crime and organize some seminars in their universities and classrooms. Most university teachers also stalk their students for their own sake. TV media plays a very positive and essential role in preventing this crime. Media empower the girls and particular persons like blind and deaf female girls and stand with them, provide them right and give awareness about this crime. Cyberstalking spread through online apps, and stalkers use personal information in the wrong way. Stalkers demand money, check, etc., from a stalking person. University students are aware and never share their pictures and videos and upload them publically on social media during this critical situation.

The implication of the Study

The nature of this study was quantitative. According to the criteria, there are some limitations due to the implication discuss in the research. Through the purposive sampling technique, data was collected in this study. This study implication will be beneficial and effective for university students, lawyers, policymakers, government leaders, and most importantly, lawmakers to solve cyberstalking issues in society during a pandemic. How to prevent this crime in the community this study will be constructive for leaders for better understanding. In detail, this study could be helpful for young generations and girls how to stop cyberstalking in this situation. Issues and through which social media app cyberstalking spread chiefly.

Recommendations:

According to the results of this study, it is recommended that there is a need for a more profound and clear reflection on the problems of social media apps used for cyberstalking everyone without any security. Many sampling in different cities gives more quick results and helps lawmakers modify the laws according to the situation. It is also recommended that university students, especially girls must take steps against cyberstalkers in this situation. Future researchers must explore different aspects and strategies to prevent cyberstalking during the pandemic situation.

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